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Research Article

**RELATIONSHIP OF HELICOBACTER PYLORI INFECTION
WITH GASTRIC CARCINOMA: A META-ANALYSIS**¹Dr Romila Safdar, ²Dr Sammia Liaqat, ³Dr Junaid Amjad¹WMO, DHQ Hosital, Mianwali, ²WMO, BHU 113 SB, Sargodha, ³MD, Latin American School of Medicine, Havana Cuba.

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Abstract:

Background: Reports in the literature regarding the relationship of *Helicobacter pylori* infection to gastric cancer are conflicting. The aim of this study was to identify the source of heterogeneity between studies.

Methods: This was a meta-analysis of observational epidemiological studies.

Results: A total of 42 studies met the selection criteria and were categorized by the type of study design: eight cohort and 34 case-control studies. The pooled odds ratio for *H. pylori* in relation to gastric carcinoma was 2.04 (95% CI: 1.69–2.45). Both patient age (OR 0.77, 95% CI: 0.68–0.89) and intestinal type cancers (OR 1.14, 95% CI: 1.05–1.25) were independent effect modifiers. Analysis of other effect modifiers showed no relationship with female gender (OR 0.76, 95% CI: 0.64–0.89), stage of cancer (advanced %) (OR 1.12, 95% CI: 0.88–1.43), anatomical location (cardia %) (OR 1.54, 95% CI: 0.32–7.39) or cohort (nested case control) studies (OR 1.72, 95% CI: 0.32–9.17). There was significant heterogeneity among the studies ($t = 2.5149$; $p = 0.001$). The quality of the studies varied considerably, with the majority of excellent studies producing positive results and the very poor to moderate studies producing mixed results.

Conclusions: *H. pylori* infection is associated with a 2-fold increased risk of developing gastric adenocarcinoma.

Key Words: gastric cancer, *H. Pylori* infection, gastric carcinoma.

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INTRODUCTION:

Gastric cancer is one of the most common malignancies in the world, although the incidence and mortality rate have been decreasing over recent decades.^{1,2} Gastric carcinogenesis is a multistep and a multifactorial process. In most cases, the initial stage is chronic gastritis, followed by atrophy, intestinal metaplasia, dysplasia, and eventually carcinoma³ the real cause of gastric carcinogenesis is not fully understood; however, several environmental factors including *Helicobacter pylori*, excessive intake of salt, bile reflux, N-nitroso compounds, and a deficiency of antioxidants have been linked with different stages of gastric carcinogenesis.³

When *Helicobacter pylori* was first identified, those that discovered it suggested that it might cause gastric cancer,⁴ which kills about a million people a year worldwide.⁵ *H. pylori* is found in the stomachs of about one-third of the adults in developed countries

(where it has been decreasing in prevalence) and in about two thirds of the adults in developing countries.⁶ It is strongly correlated with lower socioeconomic status, usually acquired in early life, probably spread from person to person, and generally persists until old age unless eradicated with specific antibiotic treatment.

In 1994 the International Agency on Research in Cancer declared *H. pylori* a 'carcinogen',⁷ but a consensus panel of the National Institutes of Health disagreed.⁸ Among these risk factors, *H. pylori* is regarded as a trigger for the sequence of carcinogenesis because there is strong evidence for *H. pylori* infection as a cause of chronic atrophic gastritis and intestinal metaplasia, two possible precancerous lesions.⁹⁻¹³ (fig 1) Epidemiological studies have shown that *H. pylori* infection is associated closely with the development of gastric cancer.¹⁴⁻¹⁵

Fig 1: *H. pylori* causes cancer:

METHOD:**Search strategy:**

For Relevant Studies the search strategy involved the major electronic databases, including MEDLINE (Index Medicus), CINAHL (Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature), CANCER CD, Biological Abstracts, and Currents Contents. If results of the same studies were presented more than once, the most recent publication was used, because of the possible impact of duplicate publication.

Inclusion criteria: Primary inclusion criteria were developed a priori for the selection of all relevant articles, which were: 1) The exposure variable must be *H. pylori* (*Campylobacter pylori* or *Campylobacter pylori*'s) infection; 2) The disease of interest must be gastric cancer, or gastric carcinoma; and 3) studies must be published after 1982 because *H. pylori* was only isolated in 1982. Secondary inclusion criteria were developed to identify studies with a case-control/cohort design, which were: 1) There were two

defined groups of subjects; 2) Cases had to be identified as having gastric carcinoma; 3) Controls must be free of gastric carcinoma; 4) Study factor (H. pylori infection) must be determined after the groups are assembled (case-control studies only); and 5) Statistical results should be in the form of an odds ratio, although proportions and raw data were acceptable as an odds ratio could be calculated (using STATA version 5.0, StataCorp.)

Quality assessment: Only the methods section of each paper was photocopied so that the authors, source, results, and discussion of the results were omitted. As there are no validated or well established instruments for the quality assessment of observational studies, a specific assessment sheet (coding manual) was developed to assist in assigning scores for each paper, thereby reducing the likelihood of substantial variation in scoring. The aspects assessed were case definition (score 0–2), representativeness of the cases (score 0–1), selection of controls (score 0–2), definition of controls (score 0–1), ascertainment of exposure to H. pylori (score 0–2), and comparability of cases and controls (score 0–5). Thus, the maximum score for a study would be 13.

Statistical Analysis: The analysis sought to identify sources of variation in the odds ratio (OR) of H. pylori on gastric cancer. Potential sources of variation were identified and combined estimates of odds ratios were obtained within strata defined by categories of such variables. Combined estimates of the odds ratio for H. pylori on gastric cancer were formed using the method of DerSimonian and Laird. Random effects estimates are reported rather than fixed effects because of marked interstudy variation. Sources of variation in the odds ratio were identified using random effects regression.

RESULTS:

Selection of Studies Initially, 12,434 abstracts were searched, and after review 1,473 were read in detail to identify studies that met the primary inclusion criteria.

More than half of the studies were excluded because they were either laboratory-based, cross-sectional, or review-type in nature. Of the 1,473 abstracts read, 42 met the secondary inclusion criteria (Tables 1 and 2); two other articles were excluded because it was concluded that the same results were published later in other journals. Overall, 42 articles that appeared in 26 different journals were entered into the meta-analysis; 22 were identified by MEDLINE, 12 by Current Contents, five by CANCER CD, and three by cross-referencing with journal reference lists. The prevalence of H. pylori was 74.1% (3212/4334) in gastric cancer and 57.4% (4527/7887) in controls. The overall pooled odds ratio for H. pylori in relation to gastric carcinoma was 2.04 (95% CI: 1.69–2.45) (Fig. 2). Effect Modifiers Table 3 shows the univariate effect of various factors on the odds ratio for H. pylori in gastric cancer. Only patient age and percentage of subjects with intestinal (vs diffuse) cancers were effect modifiers in the final model chosen by stepwise selection among all covariates. Age was coded such that the odds ratios represented the effect of 5-yr increments. Younger subjects were at lower risk (OR 0.77, 95% CI: 0.68–0.89). Percentages of cancer type were coded such that the odds ratios represented the effect of 10% increments. Intestinal cancers had a higher risk (OR 1.14, 95% CI: 1.05–1.25). Cancer site (cardia vs noncardia) and type of study (prospective vs retrospective) were not significant effect modifiers in the final model. Quality Assessment Seven studies deemed to be of high quality (quality score: 10 to 13) had positive results overall with three of these being cohort in design (The majority of negative studies were of moderate to good quality (quality scores from 7 to 9) one was high quality (38), and three poor quality (quality scores, 7)). A number of positive studies were of poor quality whereas the remainder were moderate to good quality. The odds ratio when the paper was omitted from the total group was 2.04 (95% CI: 1.68–2.46) compared with an odds ratio of 2.04 (95% CI: 1.69–2.45) if all the studies were included.

Table 1. Negative Studies Included in the Meta-Analysis and Table 2. Positive Studies Included in the Meta-Analysis

Ref.	Country	<i>H. pylori</i> -Positive <i>pylori</i> -Negative Cases	<i>H.</i> Cases	<i>H. pylori</i> - Positive Controls	<i>H. pylori</i> - Negative Controls	Odds Ratio	95% CI
15	Japan	36	14	35	15	1.10	0.43–2.86
16	Finland	136	107	693	715	1.31	0.99–1.74
17	Japan	51	21	98	45	1.12	0.60–2.07
18	USA	36	33	96	156	1.63	0.79–3.37
20	Japan	24	5	39	19	2.14	0.72–6.40
21	Japan	24	17	7	12	2.42	0.69–8.66
24	Turkey	34	12	24	16	1.89	0.69–5.21
26	Germany	65	46	56	55	1.39	0.82–2.36
29	USA	99	3	79	23	1.45	0.76–2.80
5	Netherlands	89	27	92	24	0.86	0.44–1.68
32	Japan	215	67	567	200	1.13	0.81–1.58
37	Taiwan	20	9	129	91	1.60	0.70–2.60
6	Portugal	39	41	65	15	0.54	0.24–1.19
38	Greece	34	13	34	16	1.23	0.51–2.95
39	Taiwan	90	53	448	375	1.42	0.97–2.08
42	Finland	73	11	121	25	1.50	0.70–3.22
7	China	46	39	143	112	0.93	0.57–1.54
8	Korea	96	64	83	77	1.39	0.89–2.17
46	Japan	59	23	121	46	0.97	0.54–1.75
47	India	47	28	35	40	1.91	1.00–3.67

Ref.	Country	<i>H. pylori</i> - Positive Cases	<i>H. pylori</i> - Negative Cases	<i>H. pylori</i> - Positive Controls	<i>H. pylori</i> - Negative Controls	Odds Ratio	95% CI
19	UK	20	9	54	61	2.77	1.04–7.97
22	Netherlands	54	37	142	259	2.04	1.07–3.91
23	Japan	188	25	159	54	2.55	1.48–4.44
25	Japan	93	12	80	123	13.3	5.30–35.6
27	Finland	38	16	43	41	2.21	1.01–4.91
28	Japan	95	14	81	28	2.40	1.20–4.80
30	Italy	253	54	91	71	3.66	2.33–5.74
31	China	47	4	71	31	5.10	1.70–15.5
33	USA	101	27	80	48	2.62	1.47–4.69
34	Italy	26	18	5	17	4.72	1.32–19.04
35	Japan	25	16	2	26	4.69	1.45–15.68
36	Sweden	90	22	63	40	2.60	1.35–5.02
40	Finland	36	14	10	12	3.27	1.42–7.52
41	Italy	104	44	20	34	4.02	1.99–8.17
43	Spain	41	7	33	17	3.01	1.02–8.86
44	Sweden	46	10	110	114	5.00	2.20–11.5
45	Japan	41	4	170	55	1.84	1.54–5.72
14	Germany	67	28	49	44	2.03	1.05–3.92
48	Japan	98	7	75	30	5.60	2.33–13.45
49	Korea	138	37	47	66	5.20	3.10–8.70
50	Taiwan	86	49	75	60	2.43	1.29–4.65
51	UK	119	35	102	52	1.67	1.01–2.75

fig 2: Plot of the log-odds ratios (and 95% CI) for the individual studies and combined estimate (random effects analysis). Numbers on the X axis refer to the reference number in the reference list.

Table 3. Potential Factors Influencing the Association of Helicobacter pylori With Gastric Cancer (Univariate Effects)

Factor	OR	Lower	Upper
Prospective vs retrospective	1.01	0.60	1.70
America vs Asia	0.93	0.41	2.09
Europe vs Asia	0.97	0.64	1.47
Diagnostic methods used	0.95	0.63	1.42
Year of publication	1.00	0.92	1.10
Female (%)	1.00	0.99	1.02
Age, yr (mean)	0.78	0.68	0.91
Intestinal vs diffuse (%)	1.13	1.02	1.26
Advanced vs early (%)	1.05	0.88	1.25
Cardia vs noncardia (%)	1.14	0.92	1.41
Source of cases (hospital vs other)	1.02	0.62	1.66
Source of controls (hospital vs other)	1.00	0.68	1.49
Country (Japan vs other)	1.17	0.75	1.82

DISCUSSION:

This meta-analysis has confirmed that *H. pylori* is associated with high risk of developing gastric cancer. However, the interpretation of these observations must be taken with caution as substantial heterogeneity among the studies was observed. The heterogeneity that we found among these studies does not make the results of the meta-analysis void, but it does imply that there are complex sources of heterogeneity that need

to be assessed in future research. Huang et al. recently published a similar meta-analysis of 19 studies. However, they only included studies that diagnosed *H. pylori* infection by serology and the literature search was completed by 1996. In the present report, 42 studies were included and every attempt was made to make the analysis as inclusive as possible. We observed that mixed results (both positive and negative) were obtained even in the same countries, which probably reflects in part the variable quality of the available studies. We did show that histological type (intestinal cancer) was an independent effect modifier of the association between *H. pylori* infection and gastric cancer in the overall model. A number of studies have reported a negative association between *H. pylori* and gastric cancer of the cardia, but this was not observed in the overall meta-analysis. We did show that *H. pylori* was more common in non cardia cancers overall, but this was not statistically significant. However, the anatomical location of the cardia remains a poorly defined region of the stomach; a number of studies may have inadequately differentiated among anatomical regions (cardia/fundus), thereby introducing misclassification bias, which may explain the overall lack of an association. Another potential source of misclassification bias is incorrect diagnosis of *H. pylori*.

CONCLUSION:

2-fold increased risk of developing gastric adenocarcinoma with *H. pylori* infection.

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